
**EXTRALINGUISTIC FACTORS OF ECONOMIC VOCABULARY
DEVELOPMENT: LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL ASPECT**

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Abstract: There are many studies on the translation of technical and scientific terminology, but the problem of translating specific terminology, in particular microeconomic terminology, is not sufficiently disclosed. Thus, there is a lack of intelligence on the development of a system of rules, strategies and tactics for translating professional terms, and the question of the consistency of the translator's work on the text of an economic nature is not sufficiently covered, which determines the novelty of our work. The relevance of the topic is related to the development of methodological recommendations and instructions for improving the work of a translator who transcodes microeconomic text from English to another language.

Key words: term, economic term, economic text, translation, lexical equivalent, calculation, transcription, descriptive translation method.

The study of the problem of the existence of a special component in the meaning of the word, which to a certain extent would contain knowledge about the socio-historical reality in which the language exists and functions, has been conducted by linguists for several decades.

According to the linguistic concept, the semantic plan of a word is differentiated and is not limited to one lexical concept. It also contains those incomprehensible semantic destinies that cause a person to have a set of certain associations and form the same lexical background, which, together with the lexeme and lexical concept, makes up the structure of the word:

word < lexeme < lexical concept < lexical background

There are many examples that prove the correctness of this theory. Let's compare, for example, English and Uzbek units related to the economic vocabulary: estate tax and property tax. They can be considered conceptual equivalents, since both words contain the concept of property tax belonging to a certain person, but the presented lexical units are very different in their background meanings.

If the Uzbek expression property tax means money that is collected from a person for his property, then the English estate tax is money that is collected from a person not only as a tax on his property, but also on property that does not yet belong to him, an analog of our inheritance tax.

When considering such units, a certain part of them stood out in a group of words that could be called non-equivalent, since the national and cultural content of these words is the core of their meaning, and they denote concepts that have no analogues in domestic reality.

They are particularly interesting from a country - specific point of view, since they clearly reflect the national characteristics of this vocabulary (blue chips-a term that refers to shares of any enterprise with large assets that have the highest value; collateral bonds - debt obligations guaranteed by any type of collateral (most often used in the United States); penny stock-an American term for shares, securities of a speculative nature, the exchange rate of which is less than one dollar).

The economic vocabulary also contains onomastic realities - proper names that are well - known among the carrier (Dow Jones-the index of the New York Stock Exchange, which changes daily depending on the rate of the main quoted shares (30 companies); the Old Lady of Threadneedle Street - the name of the Bank of England).

Any word is part of the lexical system of the language, its constituent element. This explains the peculiarity of the semantic structure of words in different languages. In addition, the corresponding semantic units in different languages may have different meanings, that is, they may occupy different positions in the language system [5, p.97].

Differentiation of values. The translator must face the phenomenon of ambiguity of English words at every step. But along with words that have several separate, partial meanings, there are also those that have one undifferentiated meaning, which when translated breaks up into several partial meanings. For example, when translating the word attitude, it is difficult to find a common word in Ukrainian that would cover all four main meanings of this word: attitude, behavior, position, politics.

To correctly differentiate the meaning of a word, it is necessary to know the phenomenon of concrete reality that is behind it. This is especially important when abstract concepts are concretized along with differentiation.

Much less often, when translating from English to Uzbek, the opposite phenomenon is observed: replacing a specific, specific concept with a more abstract, generic one: money still in control in all lands of the press, the radio, the moving picture, the telephone, the officials of the state, their banks and means of transportation, their police and hired agents. In the translation of the sentence - since in all countries money still controls the press, radio, cinema, Communications, government apparatus, banks and transport-the word telephone would be

inappropriate. It is necessary to replace it with a broader concept of a means of communication, which is logically included in the above list.

Semantic development - this type of contextual substitutions consists in the fact that in the absence or unsuitability of the Uzbek word-concept, another, closely related concept is used, which logically follows from it. So, translating the phrase the statement has been overtaken by time, it is necessary to abandon the literal version Time has overtaken this statement as nonsense and convey the consequence: this statement has fallen behind in life.

Antonymic translation-consists in transmitting the concept to the opposite, often with negation, that is, the antonym of the Uzbek equivalent of a given word. Antonym translation is often, if not the only, then the most convenient way to convey the semantic and stylistic meaning of many expressions.

Integral transformation-consists in a certain displacement, use in the translation of a related concept within the same generic concept.

Compensation for losses during the transfer process. Compensation is carried out in cases where in a certain passage of the text it is impossible to convey one or another characteristic feature of a given language (dialect, deviation from the language norm) or features of the characters' speech and they need to be compensated by other means. Because the translation technique compensation is most often implemented not within the sentence, but in the system of the whole text, which, in the end, is a unit of translation [1, p. 87].

Lexical and semantic substitutions (concretization, generalization, modulation).

L. Chernyakhovskaya identifies five types of lexical transformations [8, p.82]:

1. specification.
2. generalization.
3. Antonymic translation.
4. metonymic translation.
5. paraphrasing.

Analyzing the lexical and semantic transformations that are resorted to in the process of translating texts, I. Alekseeva identifies the following reasons for their occurrence::

- different signs of the same denotation in different languages;
- difference in semantic volume;
- different phrases;
- different uses of words of the same meaning [2, p. 28].

The analysis of factual material formed on the basis of the processing of translated and explanatory dictionaries, the study of contrasting material of current translations of literature of economic content, gives us grounds for the opinion that lexical and semantic transformations during the translation of terminology, in

particular the economic sector, are caused primarily by extra-linguistic factors in connection with the different vision of certain phenomena and objects by representatives of different socio-economic cultures, in particular Uzbek and English.

Similar semantic differences can be traced in the example of the tokens securities and securities, where the English version emphasizes the security of a business document.

This root cause of lexical and semantic transformations in the process of translating economic terms, in turn, is combined with the other three, influencing them and largely defining them.

The problem of the selective component of the meaning of a language sign is especially relevant for the translator when it comes to prepositions:

on farm - on the farm;

at price-by price;

ownership of means-ownership of funds;

to apply for the post - apply for the position;

pressure for money - lack of money;

to keep money with a bank -- keep money in a bank;

to buy from businesses-buy from firms.

In these examples, free prepositions are used that are not connected by phraseological combinations. Therefore, their connection with other words is not permanent, but depends on each individual case. In each case, prepositions freely enter a semantic connection with the base word. Transformations here can be traced mainly at the level of prepositions [7, p. 28].

A sufficient number of terminalizes expressed by a verb will reveal their specific meaning only in combination with certain fixed prepositions. In the following examples, prepositions have completely merged with the words they serve, and they do not have an independent meaning:

to check in-Submit against receipt;

to pension off-to retire;

to write off-cancel;

to plough back-reinvest.

The problem of word compatibility is directly related to the question of word life, since the category of the latter is essentially based on the ability of the lexeme to enter connections with other members of the sentence, primarily with those that function side by side [5, p. 164].

In the case of translation of terms from economics, the main attention should be paid to combining the noun term with adjectives that attribute it. Usually, when translating, you should avoid literalism, since the target text with verbatim

reproduced problem adjectives may sound ridiculous. Therefore, translators resort to lexical and semantic transformations:

- black money – qora pul;
- bad loan – yomon kredit;
- tough competition – kuchli raqobat;
- hidden tax – yashirin soliq;
- historical cost – eski narx;
- fat salary – yuqori maosh.

Verbs used in scientific discourse, which often resemble a common word but have a terminological meaning, also undergo semantic transformations. In the target text, the semantics of such tokens are transformed [6, p. 132]. They sound completely academic here, or at least emotionless:

- to reduce poverty
- to mushroom costs-dramatically increase costs;
- to drive investors away -scare off investors.

A special case of lexical and semantic translation transformations is the reproduction of colors that connotate and denotate professional concepts:

- green labor -unskilled labor;
- orange goods-goods that are bought relatively rarely [5, P. 55].

According to the observations of E. and G. Clark, of the eleven possible shades of colors that are usually used in the term formation of different languages, all eleven are used in English (black, white, red, yellow, green, blue, brown, purple, pink, orange, gray). One of the most used colors in the term formation of the economic sphere of the English language is red:

- red typist - bureaucrat;
- red tape - red tape;
- red -Debt, Debt, loss;
- red balance - passive (unfavorable) balance;
- to be in the red - to be in financial difficulties.

There is an explanation for the expression to be in the red: many years ago, it was a tradition to make entries in financial statements in two colors: profit was written in black, and loss was written in red. And although such a tradition no longer exists, the expression is still valid [4, p. 232].

In translation, associations with color are often leveled, although in Ukrainian terminology on finance and accounting there is a category of terms where there are references to color and, therefore, the translation of an adjective with a color Association is literal:

- Blue book
- red-ink entry

black-ink entry

So, the use of lexical-semantic transformations is inevitable in the process of translation of economic terms, since they are directly related to extralinguistic factors in the development of terminologies the different vision of socio-economic processes and concepts among different peoples.

Having analyzed all the above, we can conclude that, in general, economic terms have the same ways of transfer from English to Uzbek as all other terms. The main problem of translation of legal terms and terms-phrases is their ambiguity not only among different branches of science, but also within the economic field of the text itself. The exact meaning of the term in this case can be revealed only with the help of the context and other terms related to each other in the term-phrase.

Terms are units of language and professional knowledge that ensure the effectiveness of intercultural communication. For this reason, the equivalent translation of terminology has the greatest practical significance when translating scientific and technical texts.

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